

New approaches to post-occupancy evaluation: Unveiling the social value of housing design

Leonardo Ricaurte

School of the Built Environment, University of Reading, Berkshire, UK

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1. Introduction

This research focuses on identifying the spaces that are crucial in yielding the well-being and quality of life of residents in housing schemes. Post-Occupancy Evaluation (POE) is a promising method for assessing a building's adequacy to meet social impact goals, comply with building regulations, and deliver improved sustainability and affordability, but it tends to focus on environmental outcomes rather than the less tangible social outcomes (Hay et al., 2017; RIBA & MacDonald P., 2020; Samuel, 2020). When it comes to housing, a decision about the height of a bench in a common space, the position of windows and porches in relation to a playground, or the size of a stairwell can affect the social value of a space, and only dialogue with inhabitants can bring these nuances to light. Although architects such as Herman Hertzberger (1963, 1991) have speculated about these effects, they have not yet been subject to systematic study or reconciled with contemporary debates about the social value of housing. In the field of urban design, for instance, Jan Gehl (Gehl, 1986, 2010, 2011; Gehl et al., 2006; Gehl & Svarre, 2013) has developed scholarship and methodological approaches that rely on systematic participant observation and surveys to determine what constitutes appropriate spaces that support vibrant residential life and liveable neighbourhoods. This paper advocates that these enquiries can be further complemented by incorporating input from disciplines such as the geographies of architecture, particularly the research on 'building events' conducted by Lees and Baxter (Lees, 2001; Lees & Baxter, 2011), Jacobs et al., (2010) and Rose et al., (2010). Altogether, this can deepen the development of a more structured and evidence-based POE that is able to create and sustain learning loops that include the inhabitants' experience of spaces and shed light on the design process of housing schemes. The research question guiding the development of this paper is therefore: To what extent can the social value created by the design of housing blocks be better informed and conceptualised involving participant observation and geographies of architecture as part of post-occupancy evaluation?

2. Social value and its implications for housing design

The backdrop of the discussion is the recent interest in the English built environment sector for integrating social value as a pivotal aspect of its activity. Social value is understood as an umbrella term that encompasses the wider economic, social and environmental effects of any given activity; it is a concept that has become very prominent, especially in the UK after the advent of the Social Value Act in 2012 (UK Green Building Council, 2020, 2021). Since then, progress was made in incorporating the idea of measuring quantitatively the impact of projects in communities and society. As it can be applied to a wide array of sectors, the concept can have multiple interpretations and definitions. Efforts have been made to unify and agree on a common approach to the built environment (Raiden et al., 2018; Raiden & King, 2021).

Frameworks and tools have led to a better understanding of the protocols to assess the real social impact of projects. This is the case in the UK Green Building Council's reports *Delivering Social Value: Measurement (2020)* and *Framework for Defining Social Value (2021)*; offering an overview of the necessary steps to identify it. However, there is still a lack of standardised methods to measure social value, mainly because every development has specific circumstances, and it is not as simple as prescribing metrics hastily. In 2020 the Royal Institute of British Architects RIBA in collaboration with the University of Reading, published the *Social Value Toolkit for Architecture (Samuel, 2020)*, a document that encapsulates some of the key aspects that architects should consider to create and measure social value in their projects, a notable first step toward the involvement of architects in social value debates. *The Quality of Life Framework (URBED, 2021)* discussed below builds directly on the Social Value Toolkit. The current investigation aims to hone and theorise the process further, suggesting a more comprehensive approach to POE as a method to ascertain the real social impact of design.

3. Human behaviour, space and design: Methodologies to produce places that work

The Quality of Life Framework by The Quality of Life Foundation (QoLF) and URBED (2020) is a research-based methodology that identifies a range of themes, i.e., control, health, nature, wonder, movement and belonging, as responsible for creating liveable communities and quality of life. This document is the result of a literature review on the effects of the built environment on people's quality of life. It underscores the critical role of housing in this issue. The term 'housing' in this case alludes not only to the domestic and private spatial configuration of dwellings, but rather accentuates the importance of considering the neighbourhoods in which homes are located, the communities that live therein, and the transport links, community facilities and open spaces that serve them, as key aspects when considering health and wellbeing (URBED, 2021). This framework opened the way for the development of a POE service offered by the QoLF (QoLF, 2022) that is the vehicle to analyse and reflect on the potential of different spatial disciplines to complement the methodology. The aim is to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the ways in which space users give meaning and value to the built environment, so that architects and developers can use this information to better conceive and improve new and existing housing schemes.

On the other hand, POE, however beneficial it may be to the built environment, is not commonplace in the sector and there is a glaring lack of literature addressing this issue (Durosaiye et al., 2019; Hadjri & Crozier, 2009). POE is often regarded as an activity that demands long-term commitment and can be time-consuming. An issue that can be explained by the short-term logic of the construction sector, and the fleeting commitment of developers, especially private and profit-driven, to the communities and clients they engage with.

4. Where to look to?

The literature points at certain places within the confines of the housing block and the site as possible targets of the empirical study. Gehl (1986, 2011) and Hertzberger (1991) agree on the relevance of thresholds and transitions between levels of privacy as a key locus of successful places. Gehl refers to this as the 'edge effect' (2011, p.149), and Hertzberger as the 'in-between space' (1991, p.32). Both have to do with the design of entrances and the flow of activities throughout, and the soft transition that they can provide. Lynch (1964) also identifies the edge as an important constituent of the city image. And in *A Pattern Language* (1977), Alexander

alludes to it as the pattern of *Building the edge* which is further complemented by the one of *Activity pockets*.

Here insights from geography, particularly architectural geographies can be very valuable in informing the array of methods that can be put in place as part of a comprehensive POE. As Jacobs (Jacobs, 2006) argues, there have been calls in the field of geography for a new 'critical geography of architecture' that asks geographers to analyse the built forms up close and recognise them as "occupied performative events" (Jacobs, 2006, p.10). They suggest that spaces and places are conceptualised through the socially mediated practices they contain as part of being inhabited. Accordingly, buildings are not just static and closed masses stacked in urban blocks, but permeable entities in which users play a significant role through movement, interaction and relationships (Jenkins, 2002). Therefore, the building is conceptualised as a 'building event', "conceived of in this way, a building is always being 'made' or 'unmade', always doing the work of holding together or pulling apart" (Jacobs, 2006, p.11). In this vein, buildings are seen as assemblages of human and non-human actors who impact each other following an Actor-network theory approach. Stewart Brand (Brand, 1995) conveys a similar idea with the 'Shearing layers of change'. He asserts that this ensemble involves a hierarchical relationship, which in turn alludes to the temporal property and associated behaviour. As Brand puts it, "Site dominates the Structure, which dominates the Skin, which dominates the Services, which dominates the Space plan, which dominates the Stuff" (p.17). Thus, architecture is not static but very much alive and the 'building event' can be that vehicle to unpack residents' lived experiences of their housing estates, by looking at the feel of buildings, feelings *in* buildings and feelings *about* buildings (Rose et al., 2010). In this way, a new approach to POE can be generated that places the social interactions within the spaces under study at the centre of the enquiry. As Lees and Baxter (Baxter & Lees, 2008; Lees, 2001; Lees & Baxter, 2011) have shown, using an ethnographic approach to disentangle the different layers of 'building events' can provide rich data about community cohesion, sense of belonging and social value.

5. Conclusion

Evidence-based design is a neglected area in architectural research (Groat & Wang, 2013). Architectural practises can benefit from investigating what makes a good design from the users' perspective. Methods such as POE and participant observation can not only help to balance the scale between the social, economic and environmental facets of projects, but also reinvigorate the role of research in design. In this sense, POE can bring together different strands of research from various disciplines that seek to analyse the built environment and create new pathways to explain the phenomena. This research aims to expand the knowledge of how buildings work by focusing on the human dimension and the interaction and behaviour of inhabitants in built spaces. The empirical study, which incorporates all these considerations, is still being conducted on a specific case study and will be completed in the coming months.

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